

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

DFG reference number: NA 2012/1-1

Project number: 540160192

Project title: Study of magnetic vortex lattice in noncentrosymmetric superconductors using small angle neutron scattering

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Reporting period (entire funding period): 01.04.2024 — 31.03.2026

2 Summary

In this project, we investigated the vortex lattice of superconductors, including Re_6Zr , SrPtAs , and $\text{Y}_5\text{Rh}_6\text{Sn}_{18}$, using small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) and examined various experimental approaches to detect the vortex lattice (VL). We also carried out point-contact spectroscopy on La_3Se_4 in collaboration, where clear signatures of two-gap superconductivity were identified. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) studies on $\text{Mo}_3\text{Al}_2\text{C}$ performed using our in-house NMR facility indicate the presence of single-gap superconductivity. We further studied the low-temperature spin dynamics of double hydroxyperovskites $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$. Our findings suggest that both compounds possess a fluctuating ground state consistent with a spin-liquid phase.

3 Scientific Progress Report

(a) Original project goals

The primary goal of the project is study of magnetic vortex lattice in noncentrosymmetric superconductors (NCS) using small angle neutron scattering. This topic is important because noncentrosymmetric superconductors allow us to study unconventional superconductivity and symmetry-related effects that cannot be seen normally in conventional superconductors. Cooper pair formation generally relies on two symmetries: time-reversal and inversion symmetry. It is relatively easy to probe time reversal symmetry breaking by the application of a magnetic field; however, the removal of inversion symmetry is more challenging and only available experimentally through a NCS crystal lattice. For these systems, parity is no longer a conserved quantity, and a mixture of spin-singlet and spin-triplet order parameters becomes allowed. Our group reported a comprehensive study of the VL in NCS superconductor, Ru_7B_3 [A. S. Cameron *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **100**, 024518, 2019, A. S. Cameron *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **105**, 094519, 2022, A. S. Cameron *et al.*, J. Phys.: Condens. Matter **35**, 425602, 2023]. In this compound, a highly unusual behavior of the vortex lattice was observed, which can attribute to the spontaneous time-reversal symmetry breaking and the magnetic fields present in the superconducting phase without space inversion symmetry. In the absence of any VL structural transition, a changing magnetic field causes a continuous rotation of the VL. A theory has been developed to explain this rotation in the framework of the Ginzburg-Landau approach. So far, Ru_7B_3 remains the only superconductor where such an effect has been observed, hence it is important to verify it in other NCS systems to confirm its universality for this class of superconductors. Vortex lattices in noncentrosymmetric superconductors are still studied very little, and SANS is one of the most powerful methods to measure them directly in reciprocal space, investigate phase transitions, rotation of the vortex lattice, measure the vortex form factor, and from that extract quantitative information about the coherence length and penetration depth.

(b) Deviations from the original concept, problems in the project organization or implementation

Noncentrosymmetric superconductors have attracted significant attention in recent years, but only a few studies have focused on single crystals. Single crystals are essential for SANS measurements; however, growing them is

highly challenging. To initiate the project, I prepared a list of reported single crystals and approached the respective groups that had published studies on those single crystals. I approached Yusuke Hirose (Niigata University, Japan) for LaNiC_2 , Hiroyuki K. Yoshida (Hokkaido University, Japan) for $\text{Ag}_2\text{Pd}_3\text{S}$, Arvind Maurya (Mizoram University, India) for LaNiZn , Michael Smidman (Zhejiang University, China) for LaRhSn , Geetha Balakrishnan (University of Warwick, England) for $(\text{Y, La, Lu})\text{PtBi}$, Claudia Felser (Max Planck CPfs, Dresden) and R. P. Singh (IISER Bhopal, India) for Re_6Zr and Robert J. Cava (Princeton University, USA) for TaRh_2B_2 and NbRh_2B_2 but none of these groups were able to provide the single crystals for SANS measurement at that time. I also explored NbReSi with A. Thamizavel (TIFR Mumbai, India), but the compound could not be synthesized in a pure form. Similarly, attempts to obtain single crystals of CaPtAs from Hisashi Kotegawa (Kobe University, Japan) were not successful. I then approached Orest Pavlosiuk (Institute of Low Temperature and Structure Research Polish Academy of Science, Poland) for single crystals of YPtBi and LuPtBi . Although I obtained the crystals, their very high penetration depth made them unsuitable for SANS measurements. I submitted a proposal for SANS experiments at Institut Laue Langevin (ILL), Grenoble, France, but it was not accepted. During my PhD, I had optimized the synthesis of noncentrosymmetric superconductor La_3Se_4 in polycrystalline form, and upon moving to TU Dresden, I brought two batches of polycrystalline La_3Se_4 samples. I used one batch to initiate preliminary measurements using the in-house NMR facility and sent the other batch to Peter Samuely and Pavol Szabó at the Centre of Low Temperature Physics, Institute of Experimental Physics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Košice for point-contact spectroscopy measurements. These measurements provided valuable information on the superconducting order parameter. I learned NMR techniques and performed experiments on the polycrystalline samples of La_3Se_4 . The NMR experiments did not yield conclusive results, most likely due to the presence of secondary phases, poor phase quality, or possible degradation after exposure to air. I also submitted a proposal for muon spin relaxation (μSR) measurements on polycrystalline La_3Se_4 to investigate possible time-reversal symmetry breaking at $S\mu\text{S}$ – Swiss Muon Source at Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), Switzerland; however, the proposal was not accepted, primarily because the samples were polycrystalline. Single-crystal growth of La_3Se_4 has not been reported recently. Earlier studies from the 1900s describe the process, but it requires very high temperatures (2100°C), making growth very difficult. I discussed the possibility of growing single crystals of La_3Se_4 with Sabine Wurmehl and Saicharan Aswartham at IFW Dresden, Amir-Abbas Haghighirad at KIT University, Sang-Wook Cheong at Rutgers University, and Andrey Prokofiev at Technische Universität Wien but I was ultimately unable to obtain crystals.

Next I approached Raman Sankar (Academia Sinica, Taiwan) for Re_6Zr and received crystals; however, when I performed Laue diffraction, it revealed that the sample was polycrystalline, and single crystals could not be provided at that time. Nonetheless, SANS measurements can be performed on polycrystalline samples, and I got beam time at ILL to carry out the experiments. I then obtained high-quality single crystals of SrPtAs from Priscilla Rosa (Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA) and good single crystals of $\text{Y}_5\text{Rh}_6\text{Sn}_{18}$ from Roman Gumenuik (TU Bergakademie Freiberg, Germany). I submitted proposals and received beam time at both ILL, France, and the Swiss Spallation Neutron Source (SINQ) at PSI for SANS measurements on these samples. I have co-aligned the crystals for the SANS measurements.

$\text{Mo}_3\text{Al}_2\text{C}$, another noncentrosymmetric superconductor, was previously studied only in polycrystalline form. N. D. Zhigadlo (CrystMat, Switzerland) first synthesized single crystals of this compound, and I obtained five crystals from him. The crystals are too small for neutron experiments. However, they are suitable for NMR and scanning tunnelling spectroscopy (STS). I did NMR on this system to investigate the superconducting order parameter. The STS measurements are performed in collaboration with Jianfeng Ge at Max Planck Institute for Chemical Physics of Solids, Dresden. This work focuses on imaging vortex lattice in superconductors to understand the superconducting pairing symmetry. Currently, the measurements are underway.

(c) Overview of the main findings and discussion

Small-angle neutron scattering study of Re_6Zr

Re_6Zr is a cubic noncentrosymmetric superconductor with $T_c = 6.7$ K. Its upper critical field value is close to the Pauli limiting field, suggesting the possibility of singlet-triplet mixing. Unusual flux pinning resulting in a peak effect is observed in the magnetization data, indicating an unconventional vortex state [D. A. Mayoh *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **96**, 064521, 2017]. Zero-field μSR measurements provide strong evidence of broken time-reversal symmetry [R.

P. Singh *et al.* Phys. Rev. Lett. **112**, 107002, 2014]. This may be an indication for a mixed order parameter with a p -wave contribution. Moreover, its penetration depth is comparable to that of Ru_7B_3 , making it a promising candidate for observing vortex lattice features in this compound. SANS measurements on the polycrystalline Re_6Zr were carried out on the D33 instrument at ILL using neutron wavelengths of 4.7 Å and 3.1 Å. The sample was field-cooled (FC) to 2 K under 0.5 T magnetic field [Fig. 1], with the detector positioned 13 m from the sample. We did not observe any signal under field-cooled conditions. In principle, the field-cooling method produces an internal field distribution close to that of the equilibrium magnetization. However, the competition between Meissner expulsion and vortex pinning during FC often leads to a disordered vortex lattice, resulting in a smearing of the scattered intensity between the Bragg reflections. Therefore, we performed FC followed by a small (about 10%) damped sinusoidal modulation (‘wiggle’) of the applied field, which often leads to a more well-ordered VL structure. We also applied the wiggle-cooling approach within selected temperature ranges close to T_C . For example, measurements were performed while cooling from 4.9–4.7 K, 5.0–4.4 K, 5.1–4.7 K, and 5.5–4.9 K to examine whether the vortex lattice could be detected [Fig. 1, 2].

Fig. 1: (a), (c) SANS ($\lambda = 4.7$ Å, 3.1 Å) of Re_6Zr under FC condition. (b) Polycrystalline sample of Re_6Zr . (d, e, f, g) wiggle-field-cooled approach under various experimental conditions.

Fig. 2: (a), (b) and (c) Small angle neutron scattering of Re_6Zr with $\lambda = 3.1$ Å under wiggle-field-cooled condition.

Backgrounds were measured at zero field and subtracted from the foreground data. Only a weak isotropic background was observed in all cases. Signal integration around the expected q -values of the vortex lattice revealed no statistically significant intensity, and no distinct Bragg peaks were detected under various experimental conditions.

A powder ring of intensity in a polycrystalline sample is, of course, much harder to see than individual spots in a single crystal, which could be one of the reasons for the absence of observable vortex lattice scattering.

Small-angle neutron scattering study of locally noncentrosymmetric superconductor SrPtAs

Fig. 3: (a), (b) Small angle neutron scattering in field-cooled and wiggle-field-cooled conditions of SrPtAs. (c) Single crystals of SrPtAs and laue diffraction pattern.

Transition metal pnictides have drawn a lot of scientific interest as they present the second-largest family of superconductors after cuprates. The common feature of this family is that superconductivity occurs within a square lattice made up of transition metal elements. It possesses a hexagonal crystal structure with a non-symmorphic space group $P6_3/mmc$. Although SrPtAs is globally centrosymmetric, it lacks local centrosymmetry due to the breaking of the inversion symmetry in the As-Pt layer. Locally broken inversion symmetry and strong spin-orbit coupling SrPtAs could significantly influence its superconducting properties, similar to those typically observed in noncentrosymmetric materials. It shows time-reversal symmetry breaking [P. K. Biswas *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **87**, 180503, 2013] which may find signatures in the vortex-lattice form factor. The magnetic penetration depth of SrPtAs is approximately 239 nm, making it suitable for SANS measurements. The crystals are small, I have coaligned many such crystals using Laue for measurement [Fig. 3 (c)]. SANS measurements were performed on D33 at ILL using a neutron wavelength of 10 Å. The sample was field-cooled to 0.06 K under 0.2 T magnetic field [Fig. 3 (a)], with the detector positioned 13 m from the sample and the wiggle-cooling method was also used [Fig. 3 (b)]. Backgrounds were measured and subtracted from the foreground data. In all cases, only a weak isotropic background was observed. We looked at the signal around the expected q -values of the vortex lattice. No significant intensity was found. We also did not see any clear Bragg peaks under different experimental conditions. The lack of detectable vortex lattice scattering could result from sample disorder, which disrupts the long-range order of the vortex lattice.

Small-angle neutron scattering study of $Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$ superconductor

$Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$ ($T_c = 3$ K) is a centrosymmetric superconductor. Zero-field μ SR measurements provide strong evidence for unconventional superconductivity, revealing a spontaneous internal magnetic field that appears below the superconducting transition temperature [A. Bhattacharyya *et al.*, Sci Rep **5**, 12926, 2015]. This observation indicates that the superconducting state breaks time-reversal symmetry and may involve a mixed order parameter with a p -wave component. While such a contribution is expected in noncentrosymmetric superconductors, it is highly unusual in a centrosymmetric lattice like that of $Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$ —making it an ideal candidate for studying the vortex lattice. Moreover, the literature reports two different values for the penetration depth of $Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$: 51.4 nm [J. Akimitsu, Proc. Jpn. Acad., Ser. B **95**, 321, 2019] and 682 nm [A. Slebarski *et al.*, J. Alloys Compd. **819**, 152959, 2020]. Therefore, SANS can help us to determine the precise value of the penetration depth. SANS provides a direct way to measure the penetration depth and study the vortex lattice. For this study, I have co-aligned the $Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$ crystals for measurement [Fig. 4 (e)]. Initial SANS measurements performed at SINQ, PSI, using neutron wavelengths of 10 Å and 6 Å under different experimental conditions did not reveal any signature of the vortex lattice [Fig. 4 (a-c)]. To enhance the signal-to-noise ratio, subsequent experiments were carried out at D33, ILL, where the higher neutron flux improves the detectability of vortex lattice features. But we did not get any results from the ILL measurement either [Fig. 4 (d)]. The absence of observable vortex lattice scattering may be due to a large magnetic penetration

Fig. 4: (a), (b) Small angle neutron scattering of $Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$ ($\lambda = 10 \text{ \AA}$ and 6 \AA) under FC condition at SINQ, PSI. (c) Wigggle-field-cooled condition. (d) SANS with $\lambda = 6 \text{ \AA}$ in FC condition at D33, ILL. (e) Single crystals of $Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$ and laue diffraction pattern.

depth, which reduces field modulation and scattering contrast. It seems that the penetration depth of $Y_5Rh_6Sn_{18}$ is likely closer to the higher reported value. As a result, Bragg peaks are not observed in the SANS data.

Two-gap superconductivity in La_3Se_4 studied by Point-Contact Andreev Reflection spectroscopy

In this study, the rare-earth chalcogenide La_3Se_4 has been investigated to understand its superconducting properties. It crystallizes in a non-centrosymmetric body-centered cubic structure of the Th_3P_4 -type with space group $I\bar{4}3d$. La_3Se_4 exhibits superconductivity with a transition temperature (T_c) of approximately 8.5 K [M. Naskar *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **105**, 014513, 2022]. Point-contact Andreev reflection spectroscopy was carried out in collaboration with Peter Samuely and Pavol Szabó at the Centre of Low Temperature Physics, Institute of Experimental Physics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Košice on La_3Se_4 at low temperatures and under high magnetic fields. It shows superconductivity at $T_c = 8 \text{ K}$. Analysis of the spectra revealed the presence of two distinct superconducting energy gaps, Δ_1 and Δ_2 , characterized by $2\Delta_1/k_B T_c \sim 5.8$ and $2\Delta_2/k_B T_c \sim 2.3$ [Fig. 5]. The presence of two-gap superconductivity observed from point-contact Andreev reflection spectroscopy is also supported by heat-capacity and Hall-probe magnetization measurements. This work has been published in Phys. Rev. B **110**, 174518, 2024.

²⁷Al-NMR evidence for single-gap superconductivity in Mo_3Al_2C

Mo_3Al_2C crystallizes in a cubic noncentrosymmetric structure. Earlier studies on polycrystalline samples reported a superconducting transition at $T_c = 9.3 \text{ K}$ in polycrystalline samples. More recently, single crystals have been grown and reported [N. D. Zhigadlo *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **97**, 214518, 2018]. I performed NMR experiments on the single crystal. We report bulk superconductivity in Mo_3Al_2C by means of ²⁷Al NMR experiments, and discuss the symmetry of the superconducting order parameter together with the normal state properties. NMR measurements were done in a uniform magnetic field of $H = 4.517 \text{ T}$. In this field, the superconducting transition temperature T_c of Mo_3Al_2C is reduced to about 7.3 K [Fig. 6 (a)]. Two main conclusions are obtained from the NMR study. First, the temperature dependence of the Korringa product [Fig. 6 (c)] clearly shows the transition from the metallic state to the superconducting phase. Second, the exponential behavior of the relaxation rate in the superconducting state confirms the presence of a single superconducting energy gap. The significant drop in the ²⁷Al Knight shift [Fig. 6 (d)] below

Fig. 5: Temperature-dependent PCAR spectra with two-gap BTK model. The inset shows the temperature dependence of the energy gaps, together with BCS-like $\Delta(T)$ curves (gray and red) for $\Delta_1(0) = 2$ meV and $\Delta_2(0) = 0.8$ meV with $T_c = 8$ K, corresponding to coupling strengths $2\Delta_1/k_B T_c \sim 5.8$ and $2\Delta_2/k_B T_c \sim 2.3$. Reproduced from F. Kořuth *et al.* Phys. Rev. B 110, 174518, 2024.

Fig. 6: (a) Temperature dependence of the ^{27}Al spin-lattice relaxation rate $^{27}(1/T_1)$ for $\text{Mo}_3\text{Al}_2\text{C}$ at 4.517 T, showing the superconducting transition 7.3 K. (b) The NMR relaxation rate $1/T_1$ (at $H = 4.517$ T) as a function of $1/T$ follows an exponential law, $T_1^{-1} \propto \exp(-\Delta/k_B T)$ (c) Korrington product $1/(T_1 T)$ as a function of temperature. (d) Temperature dependence of the ^{27}Al NMR Knight shift.

Fig. 7: (a), (d) ZF- μ SR time spectra measured at various temperatures for $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$, respectively. (b), (c) Temperature dependencies of the width of the static field distribution and muon relaxation rate in zero-field μ SR measurements of $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$, respectively. (e), (f) Temperature evolution of the muon relaxation rates in ZF- μ SR spectra of $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$. Reproduced from M. Naskar *et al.* arXiv2603.01680.

T_c indicates spin-singlet superconductivity. To investigate the symmetry of the superconducting order parameter, we have carried out NMR spin-lattice relaxation rate $^{27}(1/T_1)$ experiments. Spin-lattice recovery data are described by the multiexponential expression for the spin $I = 5/2$ of ^{27}Al nuclei in the whole temperature range. For the central transition with $I = 5/2$, the time-dependent nuclear magnetization $M(t)$ follows:

$$M(t) = Ar(0.0286e^{-t/T_1} + 0.178e^{-6t/T_1} + 0.794e^{-15t/T_1}) \quad (1)$$

The relaxation of ^{27}Al nuclei can be modeled by an exponential function $T_1^{-1} \propto \exp(-\Delta/k_B T)$ [Fig. 6 (b)]. The fit provides a temperature-independent gap $\Delta/k_B = 9.52 \pm 1$ K (equivalent to $\Delta/k_B T_c = 1.3$).

It is notable that the NMR relaxation data do not show a Hebel–Slichter coherence peak just below the superconducting transition, which is typically observed in most s -wave superconductors. This suppression may arise from several factors. Impurities could reduce the coherence peak and also weaken the temperature dependence of the NMR shifts. In addition, quadrupole effects can smear out the peak, as reported in other noncentrosymmetric s -wave superconductors, such as $\text{W}_3\text{Al}_2\text{C}$ [D. Tay *et al.*, J. Phys.: Condens. Matter **34**, 194005, 2022].

Probing a spin-liquid–like ground state in double hydroxyperovskites $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$ using μ SR

In parallel with the SANS measurements, I studied the low-temperature spin dynamics of hydroxyperovskites using NMR and μ SR. I carried out the NMR experiments in-house on these samples, while the μ SR measurements were performed at PSI using the FLAME instrument. During the project tenure, I learned how to perform μ SR experiments and gained experience in analyzing and interpreting the data to certain extent.

Spin liquids remain at the forefront of the current research in low-temperature condensed matter physics. One of the central questions is understanding the role of structural disorder, as it can result in thermodynamic properties that are nearly indistinguishable from that of a true spin liquid. In recent years, double hydroxide perovskites containing magnetic transition-metal ions have been identified as a unique class of materials. These systems exhibit magnetic frustration along with correlated proton disorder. $\text{CuSn}(\text{OH})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OH})_6$ are double hydroxyperovskites with one magnetic transition-metal ion (Cu^{2+} , $S = 1/2$, or Mn^{2+} , $S = 5/2$) and nominally nonmagnetic Sn^{4+} . The magnetic

Fig. 8: (a), (d) LF- μ SR asymmetry spectra of CuSn(OD)_6 and MnSn(OD)_6 systems measured at 0.1 K. (b), (c) Field dependencies of the width of the static field distribution, muon relaxation rate in LF- μ SR measurements of CuSn(OD)_6 . (e), (f) Field evolution of the muon relaxation rates in LF- μ SR spectra of MnSn(OD)_6 . Reproduced from M. Naskar *et al.* arXiv2603.01680.

ions form a distorted fcc sublattice, which is geometrically frustrated and was theoretically considered, among others, as a potential host for spin liquids. Earlier studies in both compounds did not show long-range magnetic ordering [A. A. Kulbakov *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Mater. **9**, 033603, 2025, A. A. Kulbakov *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **112**, L100403, 2025, K. K. Parui *et al.*, Phys. Rev. B **112**, 054421, 2025].

In this study, we investigated μ SR measurements on the two extreme members of this family with the smallest and largest known magnetic moments: on the fully deuterated CuSn(OD)_6 ($S = 1/2$) and MnSn(OD)_6 ($S = 5/2$). Our measurements extend to subkelvin temperatures (0.053–50 K), which is crucial for understanding the quantum spin dynamics. Being a local probe, μ SR is highly sensitive to spin dynamics and can detect the presence or absence of tiny static internal fields. We observed no oscillations of the muon asymmetry down to 0.053 K, suggesting the absence of a well-defined static internal field in either system [Figs. 7]. The muon relaxation rates show a continuous increase with decreasing temperature, indicating persistent spin fluctuations down to 0.053 K in both compounds. Spin correlations are consistent with homogeneous spin dynamics [Figs. 8]. Our present results are fully consistent with a spin-liquid-like ground state stabilized by the randomness of exchange interactions resulting from proton disorder. More details can be found in [arXiv:2603.01680v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2603.01680v1).

Nuclear magnetic resonance studies on the double hydroxyperovskites CuSn(OD)_6 and MnSn(OD)_6

Magnetic ordering and low-energy spin dynamics in CuSn(OD)_6 and MnSn(OD)_6 were investigated using ^2H NMR ($I = 1$, $\gamma = 6.54$ MHz/T, 0.01% abundance), which provides microscopic insight into the local magnetic environment and spin behavior of frustrated magnetic systems at low temperatures. NMR spectra were recorded across a broad range of magnetic fields using a commercial probe with a Tecmag spectrometer. Spectra were acquired by recording spin echoes as a function of field, while spin-lattice relaxation times were measured using a saturation recovery pulse sequence. The ^2H NMR field-sweep spectra of CuSn(OD)_6 and MnSn(OD)_6 , measured at 15 MHz and 15.2 MHz, respectively, exhibit pronounced differences that reflect variations in structural disorder and local magnetic environments at the deuteron sites [Figs. 9]. The NMR line width provides insight into the static distribution of internal magnetic fields and allows characterization of the local nature of magnetic ordering. For CuSn(OD)_6 , the spectrum shows a distinct splitting, which might be indicative of a broad distribution of local environments. This behavior likely originates from Jahn-Teller distortions associated with Cu^{2+} ions or from correlated occupancy at the D sites. With

Fig. 9: (a), (b) Field-sweep ^2H -NMR spectra of $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$ were collected at 15.2 MHz and 15 MHz, respectively, over a range of temperatures.

Fig. 10: (a), (b) Temperature dependence of the spin-lattice relaxation rates measured at different external fields for $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$.

decreasing temperature, the shape of the spectrum changes significantly, however, overall line width has not been changed, which could be a signature of the development of quasistatic electron spin correlations on the timescale of NMR.

In addition to the spectra, the spin-lattice relaxation rate $^2(1/T_1)$ was measured. The relaxation rate provides information on the dynamical spin susceptibility, low-energy excitations, and the degree of disorder in the systems. The magnetization recovery curves were fitted using an exponential function for a spin $I = 1$ nucleus. For $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ [Figs. 10 (a)], the temperature dependent spin-lattice relaxation rate exhibits considerable field dependency on the external static magnetic field. With decreasing temperature, $1/T_1(T)$ decreases, most likely due to the suppression of spin fluctuations responsible for the enhanced relaxation rate. In the case of $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$ [Figs. 10 (b)], the fluctuations in the data set impose certain limitations on drawing any conclusions.

We did not observe the ^{119}Sn signal in either of the compounds from the NMR measurements. Since the compound lacks long-range magnetic ordering, the absence of a ^{119}Sn -NMR signal may be due to strong spin fluctuations, possible local disorder at the Sn site, or very fast relaxation times that are likely to make the NMR line extremely broad and difficult to detect. Therefore, we plan to perform ^{119}Sn Mössbauer measurements on these compounds using the in-house Mössbauer facility to gain insight into the local magnetic environment at the Sn site. Currently, the

measurements are underway.

(c) Conclusions and outlook

In conclusion, in our project NA 2012/1-1, we investigated the vortex lattice of several superconductors using SANS and explored different experimental approaches to obtain a clear vortex-lattice signal. Although a definitive signal could not be observed, these efforts helped us understand the limitations and behavior of the studied materials. We then carried out point-contact spectroscopy on La_3Se_4 in collaboration, where we identified clear signatures of two-gap superconductivity. In addition, our NMR studies on $\text{Mo}_3\text{Al}_2\text{C}$ indicate the presence of single-gap superconductivity. One of the scientific results from our project has already been published, and another has been submitted to *Phys. Rev. Lett.* Other results, particularly the NMR studies on $\text{Mo}_3\text{Al}_2\text{C}$ and double hydroxyperovskites, are highly promising and are being prepared for publication.

Furthermore, our SANS measurements on noncentrosymmetric superconductors could provide a useful starting point for future studies. In this project, we studied Re_6Zr in polycrystalline form; performing SANS experiments on single crystals could give clearer details of the vortex lattice. Similarly, synthesizing single crystals of La_3Se_4 would be very useful. This would allow the study of its superconducting properties, including time-reversal symmetry breaking using μSR , superconducting order parameter using NMR and the vortex state using SANS. Since the superconducting order parameter in La_3Se_4 is still not well studied, further work on this compound could offer new insights into its behavior and contribute to a better understanding of noncentrosymmetric superconductors in general.

In addition to superconductors, we have also studied the low-temperature spin dynamics of double hydroxyperovskites. This work will open many new research directions. It is useful for people interested in quantum magnetism and frustrated systems. It is also relevant for those studying proton dynamics, such as hydrogen storage. Mineralogists may be interested because many hydroxyperovskites are natural minerals. It should also encourage the search for new materials combining magnetism with proton disorder.

4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

F. Košuth, N. Potomová, Z. Pribulová, J. Kačmarčík, **M. Naskar**, D. S. Inosov, S. Ash, A. K. Ganguli, J. Šoltýs, V. Cambel, P. Szabó, P. Samuely; *Two-gap superconductivity in the noncentrosymmetric La_3Se_4 compound*. *Phys. Rev. B* **110**, 174518 (2024), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.110.174518>

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

M. Naskar, A. A. Kulbakov, K. K. Parui, J. A. Krieger, T. J. Hicken, H. Luetkens, E. Häußler, T. Doert, D. C. Peets, H.-H. Klauss, D. S. Inosov, R. Sarkar; *Spin-liquid-like ground states in the double hydroxyperovskites $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$ evidenced by μSR spectroscopy*. [arXiv2603.01680](https://arxiv.org/abs/2603.01680)

Conferences:

Oral: Spin-liquid-like ground states in the double hydroxyperovskites $\text{CuSn}(\text{OD})_6$ and $\text{MnSn}(\text{OD})_6$ evidenced by μSR spectroscopy, [DPG March Meeting 2026](#), Dresden, Germany, Mar 8-13, 2026, Session number: TT 72.3, Serial number: TT 499

Poster: Two-Gap Superconductivity in the Noncentrosymmetric La_3Se_4 , [DPG March Meeting 2025](#), Regensburg, Germany, Mar 16-21, 2025, Session number: TT 11.17, Serial number: TT 142

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

None